

RESEARCHING THE EFFECT OF IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA ON THE RESILIENCE OF THE COLLECTIVE COLLECTED BASED ON PERENNIAL PLANTS (NETTLE, DOG ROSE, HAWTHORN) OBTAINED.

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Researching the effect of iron deficiency anemia on the resilience of the collective collected based on perennial plants (nettle, dog rose, hawthorn) obtained.

Justification: The flora of Uzbekistan is rich in perennial plants, which are widely used in folk medicine. Perennial products obtained from plants are low in harmful substances according to the regulations, and they have no side effects. Using these plants is one of the ways to strengthen human health. They contribute to faster recovery after illness, improving vitality, and also protect you from the negative effects of the surrounding environment. Therefore, obtaining and studying herbal remedies from perennial plants is important for medical practice. For this purpose, a collection of perennial plants against anemia was created. It includes several plants such as nettle, dog rose, and hawthorn.

Purpose of the research: This study aimed to investigate the effect of a collection consisting of 10% infusions of perennial plants: nettle, dog rose, hawthorn on the blood morphology in experimental post-hemorrhagic anemia (PHA).

Methods and procedures: Experiments were conducted on 25 adult rabbits of both sexes, weighing 2-3 kg each. PHA was induced by increasing blood loss from the right auricular vein of rabbits. Two days after PHA induction, the rabbits were divided into five groups: 1) control group received distilled water in therapeutic preparation volume; 2) group treated with collection infusion at a dose of 10 ml/kg; 3) group administered ferrous preparation orally once a day for 30 days at a dose of 25 mg/kg for comparison. Blood samples were taken before, 2 days after bleeding, and after 15 and 30 days of treatment. The morphological composition of peripheral blood was analyzed, including hemoglobin level (g/L), red blood cell count ($\times 10^{12}$), color index, hemoglobin content in a single red blood cell in PG, iron content in serum (mmol/L), and peripheral blood elements calculated by Goryaev's chamber using diluting fluid. The iron content in the blood was determined by the Hostex diagnostic kit (Italy) using a calorimetric method. The obtained results were reanalyzed using the method of variation statistics taking into account the student's t-test.

Results: The experiment results indicated that PHA occurred in rabbits within two days after bleeding, indicating changes in the morphological composition of peripheral blood. Thus, hemoglobin level decreased from 135 ± 2.5 to 102 ± 1.3 g, red blood cell count decreased from 5.0 ± 0.5 to 3.9 ± 0.8 , color index decreased from 0.81 ± 0.09 to 0.73 ± 0.02 , and hemoglobin content in a single red blood cell decreased from 27 ± 2.5 to 23.75 ± 1.5 g, while iron content in the blood decreased from 18.65 ± 0.05 to 9.65 ± 0.05 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ ($P < 0.05$). Anemia was accompanied by morphological changes in red blood cells, particularly anisocytosis and poikilocytosis. After 30 days of treatment with experimental PHA infusion and ferrous preparation, there was almost no difference in the morphological composition of peripheral blood parameters compared to the control group that was not treated for 30 days.

Recovery in the control group was much slower, and the observed indicators did not even approach the parameters of the group that was not treated for 30 days.

Conclusion: The infusion of the collection at a dose of 10 ml/kg in PHA exhibited specific characteristics against anemia comparable to ferrous preparation. The infusion contributed to the normalization of the morphological composition of peripheral blood and free iron content in the blood. In other words, the preparation responded to all parameters.

List of used literature

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